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Attitude toward the work and its influence on the Individual work performance of employees: Basis for Attitude Management

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Abstract. This study aims to determine the effect of the attitude of employees toward work and work performance. To establish a theoretical foundation of the study, related literature was reviewed. The study used descriptive assessment and correlational research design. The data were gathered through questionnaires and the data were interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics in which weighted mean was used to measure the level of extrinsic and intrinsic work values and work performance. While Pearson r correlation was used to measure the correlation between attitude toward work and work engagement of employees. The study found that overall there is a significant correlation between attitude toward work and work performance. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

Keywords. Attitude, cognitive and affective attitude, work performance

Introduction

Employees' performance matters much to the survival and competitiveness of any organization. The vision and mission of an organization can be achieved only through employees who are willing to exert effort and extra effort to carry out their duties and responsibilities assigned to them. This is the main concern of employers or managers. Managers must evaluate work performance regularly to find out if the employees are performing or not and then from the result of the evaluation, the manager would know that some employees are not performing and it is only then the manager finds out the reason behind the underperformance and propose interventions to remedy the problems. Performance evaluation is an evaluation of a job assigned to a person. It measures the performance of the employees on the job within a specific period and through it, the manager may know if the employees meet or fail the expectations (Villanova University, 2020). Underperformance can be caused by many factors such as knowledge on the job, their feeling toward the job, skills, and motivation. Therefore, the management should provide tools to evaluate the performance of employees to determine the factors that affect their performance and the performance evaluation tools must not only measuring their knowledge and skills but it can also include their feeling toward the job. Through performance evaluation, the managers can identify the problem and address the

problem. Thus, performance evaluation benefits the employee and the organization at the same time (Laurenz, 2011). Without the performance evaluation, problems can be prolonged and consequently will lead to the failure of the organization.

As we have pointed out earlier that performance is caused by many factors because there are no single factors that cause the performance of employees. There can be a lot of factors that affect the work performance of employees such as attitude toward the work which can be related to their knowledge and feelings toward the job, skills, and motivation. There have been studies measuring skills and performance and motivation and performance such as Wade and Parent (2002) pointed out that deficiencies in technical and organizational skills lead to lower job performance. This was also confirmed by Tamkin (2005) in his presentation that skills contribute to business performance. In the case of the influence of motivation toward work performance, the study also shows that there is a strong correlation between work motivation and individual and organizational performance (Deressa & Zeru, 2019). However, studies on the effect of attitude toward work and performance have a mixed result as pointed out by Omolayo and Oluwafemi (2012) that there is no significant correlation between attitude toward work and work performance in the private sector. This was also confirmed by the study of Susanty and Maradipta (2013) on the influence of attitude toward work and work commitment and work performance. Their study found that there is a positive correlation but the correlation is not significant. But the study of Abdalkrim and Elhalim (2016) showed otherwise that there is a correlation between attitude toward work and work performance and work satisfaction. The mixing result can be caused by the context of the study because these studies are conducted in different countries such as Nigeria, Indonesia, and Saudi Arabia as Schwarz and Bohner (2001) pointed out that the influence of attitude toward a behavior is context-dependent. Context can mean the place or the situation in which the person stays and experience the object of the attitude and therefore influences the behavior. The context can serve as a moderating variable in which moderate the influence of attitude toward the behavior.

Motivated by the mixed result of the study on the relationship between attitude toward work or job and work performance, the current study is carried out. Attitude is within the domain of social psychology and the current study does not problematize the concept of attitude but we are using the social psychology concept of attitude and its influence on behavior. The researcher adopts the concept of Allport (1968) that attitude is a key predictor of behavior. The concept of Allport (1968) was strengthened further by Ajzen (1993) that attitude affects behavior. Though their concept may not be so conclusive that the only factor affecting behavior is attitude. Other studies contradicted their positions such as Corey (1937), Freeman and Ataoev (1960), as cited by Ajzen (1993), Dean (1958). Their study concluded that there is no correlation between attitude and behavior. Wicker (1969) also confirms the same finding.

Given those conflicting findings, the current researcher still believes that different workplace environments may affect or may not affect the attitude of employees toward work. There have been no studies yet to find out the effect of employees' attitude toward their job can affect the work performance in the Philippine Context, particularly Divine Word Colleges' context. This belief is supported by the researcher's findings of previous studies related to the influence of attitude toward behavior in the context of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region, Philippines. For example, Abun, et.al (2019) investigated the cognitive and affective attitude of teachers toward research and their behavioral intention to conduct research and the study found that there is a correlation between the two variables. Abun and Agoot (2017) conducted a study to measure the environmental attitude and environmental behavior of the Divine Word Colleges' Senior High School and it was found that there is a correlation between eco-centric attitude and environmental behavior. The context here is the situation and the

experience of employees of the workplace can affect their attitude toward the work and therefore the title of the study is: “Assessing the attitude toward work and work performance of Divine Word Colleges’ employees in Ilocos Region: the Divine Word Colleges’ Context”. The context is emphasized because different contexts can have different attitudes toward work. The culture or practices of a certain institution can affect the attitude of employees of that particular institution toward work.

The study is divided into five parts: the first part is the rationale of the study in which it explains the background of the study and the purpose of the study. The second part is about the related literature that explains different theories of the study. The third part is the research methodology which discusses the research design, population of the study, the locale of the study, the research instrument, and statistical treatment of the study. Four-part are empirical data and analysis and the fifth part is the Result and discussion and conclusion.

Review of Related Literature

The purpose of the literature review is to review the ideas and findings of the previous literature related to the current study. This is to establish the theoretical foundation of the current study and also to determine the gap that has not been pursued in the previous studies. There has been literature that has discussed the concept of attitude and its influence on the behavior of a person. This part is focusing on different pieces of literature that have discussed the following topics.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Concept of Attitude and its influence on behavior

There are a lot of definitions of attitude. For example, Perloff (2016) defined attitude as a mental and emotional disposition of a person toward a certain object (Perloff, 2016). Myers (2013) defines attitude as a favorable and unfavorable reaction of someone toward a certain object or someone which is shown through one's beliefs, feelings, and intended behavior. It is a favorable and unfavorable evaluative reaction toward something or someone (Myers, 2013). Ajzen (1993) understands attitude as an individual disposition to react favorably and unfavorably toward a certain object, person, institution, or event. Wood (2000) defines attitude as an evaluation of attitude object which can range from positive to negative evaluation. Attitude objects can be person, object, event, activities, or ideas (Wood, 2000). Liska (1974) pointed out that attitude is a favorable and unfavorable evaluative reaction toward something, object, or person. Eagly and Chaiken (1998) contend that attitude is a psychological tendency toward a particular entity with some degree of favor or disfavor. Though these definitions are offered by different theorists, however, the content of their definition on attitude is the same, that attitude is an individual reaction, either verbal or non-verbal (Ajzen, 1993) toward a certain person, object, event, or institution. It is an internal disposition of someone toward something and can be expressed through verbal and nonverbal reactions. These definitions have in common, that they have an evaluative structure toward the attitude object (Ajzen, 2001). Therefore, though attitude is a latent disposition, it can be measured through verbal or nonverbal reactions.

There are three components of attitude and they are ***cognitive, affective, and conative or behavioral components*** (Rossenberg & Hovland, 1960), Ajzen (1993), and these three components are interrelated. One can affect others. The cognitive component of the attitude refers to the beliefs, and thoughts related to the attitude object. Affective components have something to do with the feelings or emotions of the person toward the attitude object. Lastly is conative components are related to the way how a person behaves toward the attitude object.

Again the way how a person reacts to the attitude object can be positive or negative. Thus all components of attitude are positive and negative. One may have positive and negative beliefs or thoughts about a certain object, or one may have a negative or positive feeling about a certain object. These positive or negative attitudes, positive or negative feelings affect the behavior of the person toward the object.

Attitude and behavior are two components that cannot be separated because attitude can influence the behavior of a person. Ajzen (1993) had argued that attitude has a predictive ability that can explain the behavior. Earlier, Allport (1935) had argued that attitude is a key predictor of behavior. Liska (1974) also argued that attitude with social support affects the behavior of a person. Ajzen and Fishbein (2005) had also pointed out that people's behavior follows from their beliefs, attitudes, and intentions. Though Ajzen (1993) recognized that attitude relation to behavior can be influenced by many mediating variables, however, Ajzen (1993) still contends that accurate prediction of behavior can be determined by assessing attitude and behavior at a compatible level of generality.

The discussion on the attitude-behavior relations has been controversial because though some theorists are holding on to the belief that attitude predicts the behavior, however many also social psychologist have argued otherwise, that the behavior of people is not always aligned with their beliefs. For example, Chaiklin (2011) argued that the relationship between attitudes is not always symmetrical or not always perfectly aligned. Abun, et.al. (2020) made the same conclusion after he conducted a study on the relationship between the attitude of students toward corruption and their behavioral intention to corrupt in the future. The study found that there is no correlation between their attitude toward corruption and their behavior. Though they agree that corruption is morally bad but such perception does not lead them not to corrupt in the future. They still corrupt because everybody is doing it. The earlier study conducted by Dean (1958) on the relationship between attitude toward labor unions and their participation in labor union meetings found that there is no correlation. The study of Wicker (1969) had already found that there is no correlation between attitude and behavior. The study of Wicker (1969) had encouraged other social-psychologists to abandon the study on attitude and behavior correlation. Instead of studying the relationship between attitude and behavior, the group recommended studying the social context and behavior (De Fleur & Westie, 1958, Deutscher, 1969). Given those controversial findings, Ajzen argued that the discrepancy is caused by other moderating factors. Attitude is assumed to interact with other moderating variables in their effect on behavior (Ajzen, 1993 cited from Fazio & Zanna, 1981, Snyder, 1982, Warner & DeFleur, 1969). Factor like personality characteristics such as self-monitoring, and the need for recognition and confidence play as moderating variables in the attitude-behavior relation. Though the moderating variables are difficult to prove to intervene in the correlation between attitude and behavior, Ajzen (1993) still maintained his position that attitude-behavior relation is influenced by other moderating variables. Ajzen and Fishbein (1977, 2000) still maintain that attitude is key to predict behavior. This is in support of the position of Allport (1968) that attitude is the key predictor of behavior and "the most distinctive and indispensable concept in contemporary American social psychology" (p.59). Recent studies somehow support these arguments. Abun, et.al (2018) measured the environmental attitude and environmental behavior of Catholic Colleges' employees and the study found that the environmental attitude of employees leads them to their environmental behavior. Earlier, Fitzsimmons and Douglas (2005) also studied the entrepreneurial attitude of students and the intention to do business in the future and the study also found that there is a correlation between entrepreneurial attitude and behavioral intention to do business in the future.

Attitude is not innate in the sense that it is given at birth as part of human nature but attitude is formed through life experience. Ajzen (1993) argued that someone formed an attitude toward a certain object or person through his/her association with that attitude object. According to Ajzen (1993), a person can have many beliefs about certain objects but he/she can attend to only a small number of beliefs, and this form salient beliefs of the person toward the object. The salient beliefs are considered determinant factors of a person's attitude. Abun, (2018) contends that the attitude is formed by the culture where the person is raised and his idea is similar to the idea of Donald (2002) and Hofstede as cited by Brown (1995). Donald argued that culture plays an important role in the formation of brain functioning and even brain structure. Indirectly he pointed out the power of culture in the formation of beliefs and ideas of a person toward a certain object, person, or events. Since the human mind is programmed by culture, Brown (1995) argued that it makes the difference why people have a different attitude and it distinguishes one group from another group.

Attitude toward work and Work Performance.

The concept of attitude toward work cannot be explained without going back to the concept of an attitude of Ajzen (1993), Myers (2013), Perloff (2016), Liska (1974) that attitude is a cognitive, affective, and conative reaction toward a certain object, event, person or institution. In line with this concept, attitude toward works means a cognitive, affective, and conative reaction of employees toward the work. It is about what employees know or think and feel about the work and how they would react behaviourally toward the work. The reactions of people toward the work can be favorable and unfavorable. In short, attitude is evaluation because it involves a preference for or against the attitude object (Cunningham & Zelazo, 2007) and it is "it is our relatively enduring evaluation of attitude object". These reactions are the result of their exposure or experience toward the work as McLintic (2016) argued that "attitude is formed over time as we expose to stimuli and make an evaluation". People tend to react favorably toward the work when they have encountered good or positive experiences about the work and they tend to react unfavorably when they did not have a good experience or when they did not gain anything from the work (McLintic, 2016, Milar and Milar 1996). Bem (1970) had argued that attitude is formed through direct or indirect experience through the persuasion of others or media.

Though there are a lot of psychological debates on the enduring relationship between attitude and behavior, however, many still believe that attitude affects behavior (Ajzen, 1993, Allport, 1968, Liska, 1974). Attitude-behavior relation theory (Ajzen, 1993) thus argues that attitude affects the behavior of the person in a sense that people would behave toward a certain object, person, or institution or work or job favorably or unfavorably depending on his/her attitude toward the work. Thus, a person needs to have a positive view of the work to improve his/her performance (Reys, 2020). Bianca (2020) had already pointed out that employees' attitude impacts their work performance. The same is pointed out by McQuerrey (2019) that negative and positive attitude toward the work impacts the performance and workplace. A positive attitude toward work would not only affect organizational and individual performance but is a key to success (Gill, 2020). Their position is supported by the study of Susanty and Maradipta (2013) that a positive attitude toward work has a positive effect on job performance. This is also pointed out in the study of Ahmad and Shah (2010) that attitude toward work can affect organizational commitment. Thus the challenge of management is how to change a negative attitude toward work into a positive attitude toward work to reverse the negative effect on the performance (Post, 2019). Aurora University study's (2019), Farouk (2014), Berta, et.al (2018) also found in its study that job-related attitude affects the job involvement of employees and productivity, that there is a significant relationship between attitude toward work and work

performance and productivity of the individual employee. In other words, individual work performance has something to do with the employees' attitude toward their work.

Individual performance can be defined as the behaviors that are relevant to the attainment of the goal of the organization (Campbell, 1990). Attitude toward work can affect the three components of individual work performance and they are task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior. Task performance can be defined as “the proficiency by which individuals perform the core technical task central to his/her job” (Campbell, 1990, cited by Koopmans, et.al, 2014). The second component of individual performance is contextual performance. Borman and Motowidlo, (1993, cited by Koopmans, 2014) contend that contextual performance is “the behavior that supports the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical core must function”. Lastly is the counterproductive behavior component. It is defined as “the behavior that harms the well-being of the organization” (Rotundo and Sackett, 2002, cited by Koopmans, et.al. 2014).

Conceptual Framework
Independent Variables

Dependent Variables

Source: Ajzen (1993) and Koopmans, et.al (2014).

Figure 1: It reflects the relationship between employees' attitudes toward work and their job performance. Employees' attitude toward work explains the job performance of employees.

Statement of the Problems

The study tries to determine the correlation between the attitude of employees toward their work and their work performance. It specifically answers the following questions:

1. What is the attitude of employees toward work in terms of:
 - a. Cognitive attitude
 - b. affective attitude
2. What is the job performance of employees in terms of
 - a. Task performance
 - b. Contextual performance
 - c. Counterproductive behavior

3. Is there a relationship between employees' attitudes toward work and their job performance?

Assumption

A positive and negative attitude toward work can affect the work performance of employees. Different components of attitude can influence the behavior of employees in performing their work and these components can be measured.

Hypothesis

Bianca (2020) and McQuerrey (2019) argued that employees' attitude toward work affects their job performance or productivity.

Scope and delimitation of the Study

The study covers the employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region and it covers only the cognitive and affective attitude toward work. The limitation of the study is that it measures attitude through verbal expression which is measured through questionnaires. To completely capture the latent attitude of the person, verbal and nonverbal expression of attitude must be measured and this is homework for future researchers.

III. Research Methodology

The study is carried out to find out the attitude of employees toward their work and its correlation with the individual work performance (IWP) of Divine Word Colleges' employees in the Ilocos Region. Thus this part discusses the research design, the locale of the study, population of the study, data gathering instruments, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The nature of this study is a descriptive study and therefore it used a descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design. The fundamental characteristics of descriptive research are to describe what is found in the data collected through questionnaires and statistical data. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, phenomena, or relationship variables. In short, it describes "what is" about the data (Ariola, 2006, cited by Abun, 2019).

To carry out the study, the descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational method are deployed. The study would determine the level of attitude of employees toward their work and their work performance.

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region that is composed of Vigan. Divine Word College of Vigan and Divine Word College of Laoag. Divine Word College of Vigan is belonged to the Province of Ilocos Sur and is located within the heritage city of Vigan. Divine Word College of Vigan is run by the Congregation of the Divine Word Missionaries or known as Society of the Divine Word or in Latin, *Societas Verbi Divini* (SVD). While Divine Word College of Laoag belongs to Ilocos Norte Province and is located in Laoag City.

Population

The population of the study was composed of all employees of Divine Word College of Vigan and Divine Word College of Laoag. Since the total numbers of employees are limited, and therefore total enumeration is the sampling design of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study utilized questionnaires. The first part of the questionnaires on the attitude toward work was made by the researcher and validated by a panel of experts and the second part on the work performance was adapted from the IWPQ of Koopmans, et.al (2014).

Data Gathering Procedures

In compliance with the research integrity and ethical requirement in conducting research, the data gathering process was followed. The researcher sent a letter to the President of the Colleges, requesting them to allow the researcher to flow his questionnaires in the college they manage. The researcher personally met the Presidents and employees and requested them to answer the questionnaires.

The retrieval of questionnaires was arranged between the President’s representative and the researcher with the help of employees and faculty of the college.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Since the nature of the study is descriptive research, therefore descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean is used to determine the level of cognitive and affective attitude toward their work and their work performance and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation of employees’ attitude toward work and work performance. The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

IV. Empirical Data and Analysis

This part presents data that were gathered through questionnaires. This is the crucial importance of the validity and quality of research. As scientific research, it has to be supported by data to prove that actual study has been done. Thus, the presentation of data follows the statement of the problems of the study.

Problem 1: 1. What is the attitude of employees toward work in terms of:

- a. Cognitive attitude,
- b. affective attitude

Table 1. The Attitude of Employees toward Work in terms of Cognitive Attitude

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I know my work.	4.18	A
2. I believe that I can perform my work easily.	3.99	A
3. I have been in the work for quite some time.	3.95	A
4. I am familiar with all the details of my work.	3.98	A
5. I have the skills to carry out my work.	3.99	A
6. I can carry out my work without the help of others.	3.82	A
Composite Mean	3.99	A

Source: Abun, Magallanes, Foronda, & Encarnacion, (2019).

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *Strongly agree/Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

As gleaned from the data, it shows that as a whole, the attitude of employees toward work in terms of their cognitive attitude attained a composite mean of 3.99 which is described as “agree/high”. This signifies that the attitude of employees toward their work in terms of cognitive attitude is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. This rating implies that the knowledge of employees toward their work is considered high but not very high. Even if the items are taken separately, they all indicate the same level of mean rating which is described as "agree/high" such as "knowing their work (4.18), believing that they can perform their work (3.99), having been in the work for quite sometimes (3.95), familiarity with the details of their work (3.98), having the skills (3.99), and the confidence that they can carry out their work without the help of others" (3.82).

Table 2. The Attitude of Employees toward Work in terms of Affective Attitude

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I am happy with my work.	4.02	A
2. I am always eager to show up for work.	3.95	A
3. My work gives me satisfaction.	3.94	A
4. I feel good because I can perform my work.	4.02	A
5. My work is important to me.	4.10	A
6. My work gives me a sense of meaning.	4.07	A
Composite Mean	4.02	A

Source: Source: Abun, Magallanes, Foronda, & Encarnacion, (2019).

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *Strongly agree/Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

Based on the data presented in the table, it reveals that as a whole, the attitude of employees toward their work in terms of affective attitude obtained a composite mean rating of 4.02 which is interpreted as "agree/high". This indicates that the attitude of employees toward their work in terms of emotional attitude is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. This result points out that employees not only knowing their job intellectually but even emotionally they are happy with their job because it gives them meaning and satisfaction in life. Even when the items are taken singly, they all fall within the same level of mean rating which is interpreted as "agree/high" such as “being happy with their work (4.02), eager to show up for work (3.95), giving them satisfaction (3.94), feeling good because they can perform their work (4.02), the work is important to them (4.10) and giving meaning to them” (4.07).

Table 3. Summary of Attitude toward Work

ITEMS	Mean	DR
Cognitive Attitude	3.99	A
Affective Attitude	4.02	A
Overall Mean	4.00	A

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

The data on the summary table portrays that as a whole the attitude of employees toward their work obtained an overall mean rating of 4.00 which is described as "agree/high". This overall mean rating depicts a fact that employees' attitude toward their work is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. Even when the variables are taken singly, they all are rated within the same level of mean rating which is described as "agree/high" such as cognitive attitude (3.99) and affective attitude (4.02). This result suggests that intellectually employees know their work well and emotionally they love their job because it is important to them and giving meaning to them.

Problem 2: What is the job performance of employees in terms of

- a. *Task performance*
- b. *Contextual performance*
- c. *Counterproductive behavior*

Table 4. Job performance of employees in terms of Task Performance

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I manage to plan my work so that it was done on time.	3.91	A
2. My planning was optimal.	3.87	A
3. I kept in mind the results that I have to achieve in my work.	3.96	A
4. I was able to separate main issues from side issues at work.	3.93	A
5. I knew how to set the right priorities.	3.95	A
6. I was able to perform my work well with minimal time & effort.	3.80	A
Composite Mean	3.90	A

Source: Koopmans, et.al (2014).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

As reflected on the table, the data reveals that as a whole the job performance of employees in terms of task performance obtained a composite mean rating of 3.90 which is interpreted as "agree/high". The result signifies that employees' task performance is not very high but high and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. This implies that employees agree that they perform their job to a high level. The result indicates that the employees are proficient enough to perform the technical task. Even when the items are taken separately, they all receive

the individual mean rating within the same description as “agree/high” such as “planning their work to finish on time (3.91), planning is optimal (3.87), keeping in mind the result that they are going to achieve (3.96), the capability to separate the main issue from side issues at work (3.93), knowing how to set the right priorities (3.95), and performing their work well with minimal time and effort”(3.80).

Table 5. Job performance of employees in terms of Contextual Performance

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I took on extra responsibilities.	3.84	A
2. I started a new task myself when my old ones were finished.	3.77	A
3. I took on a challenging work task, when available.	3.85	A
4. I worked at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date.	3.92	A
5. I worked at keeping my job skills up-to-date.	3.98	A
6. I came up with creative solutions to new problems.	3.84	A
7. I kept looking for new challenges in my job.	3.85	A
8. I did more than was expected of me.	3.85	A
9. I actively participated in work meetings.	3.87	A
10. I actively look for ways to improve my performance at work.	3.91	A
11. I grasped opportunities when they presented themselves.	3.88	A
12. I knew how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly.	3.82	A
Composite Mean	3.87	A

Source: Source: Koopmans, et.al (2014).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

As manifested by the data on the table, it tells that as a whole, the job performance of employees in terms of contextual performance gained a composite mean of 3.87 which is described as “agree/high”. This composite mean portrays the fact that the job performance of employees in terms of contextual performance is considered not very high but high and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. This result points out that the behavior of employees supports the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical skills are performed (Borman & Motowidlo, (1993). Even when the items are taken separately, they all gain the same level of mean rating which is described as “agree/high” such as “taking extra responsibilities (3.84), starting a new task when the old ones were finished (3.77), taking on a challenging work task, when available (3.85), working at keeping their job knowledge up-to-date (3.92), working at keeping their job skills up-to-date (3.98), coming up with creative solutions to new problems (3.84), keeping looking for new challenges in my job (3.85), doing more than was expected of them (3.85), actively participating in work meetings (3.87), actively looking for ways to improve their performance at work (3.91), grasping opportunities when they presented themselves (3.88), and knowing how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly” (3.82).

Table 6. Job performance of employees in terms of Counterproductive Work Behavior

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I complained about unimportant matters at work.	3.30	SWA
2. I made problems greater than they were at work.	3.44	A
3. I focused on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects.	3.53	A
4. I spoke with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work.	3.36	SWA
5. I spoke with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of my work.	3.38	SWA
6. I did less than was expected of me.	3.46	A
7. I managed to get off from a work task easily.	3.33	SWA
8. I sometimes did nothing, while I should have been working.	3.46	A
Composite Mean	3.41	A

Source: Source: Koopmans, et.al (2014).

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *Strongly agree/Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

As seen in the data, it gives a picture that as a whole the job performance of employees in terms of counterproductive behavior attained a composite mean rating of 3.41 which is translated as “agree/high”. Such composite mean rating points out that the job performance of employees in terms of counterproductive behavior is considered not very high but high and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. This evaluation signifies that the behavior that harms the organizational well-being is high. Even when taking them singly, some items are rated within the description of “somewhat agree and agree” such as “complaining about unimportant matters at work (3.30), making problems greater than they were at work (3.44), focusing on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects (3.53), speaking with colleagues about the negative aspects of their work (3.36), speaking with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of their work (3.38), doing less than was expected of them (3.46), manage to get off from a work task easily (3.33) and sometimes doing nothing, while one should have been working” (3.46).

Table 7. Summary of Job Performance of Employees

ITEMS	Mean	DR
Task Performance	3.90	A
Contextual Performance	3.87	A
Counterproductive Work Behavior	3.41	A
Overall Mean	3.73	A

Source: Koopmans, et.al (2014).

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *Strongly agree/Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat agree/Moderate*

1.81-2.60

Disagree/Low

1.00-1.80

Strongly disagree/Very Low

The summary table shows that as a whole, employees' job performance gained a composite mean rating of 3.73 which is described as "agree/high". It just simply means that the job performance of employees with the three sub-variables is not very high but high and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. On one hand, employees have proficient knowledge of the technical aspect of their work and on the other hand, their behavior supports the organizational, social and psychological environment in which they perform their job. But taking it singly, the data reveals that their counterproductive behavior is also high. This implies that though they have proficient knowledge and technical skills about their work and proper behavior that support work environment, however, employees also have counterproductive behavior which can affect task performance and contextual performance. Counterproductive behavior refers to the behavior that harms the well-being of the organization.

Table 11. Relationship between attitude toward work and job performance

		Task Performance	Contextual Performance	Counter productive
Cognitive Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.644**	.605**	-.001
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.991
	N	171	171	171
Affective Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.663**	.700**	.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.672
	N	171	171	171

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the Pearson r correlation table, the data reveals that as a whole there is a significant correlation at 0.01 level (2-tailed) between attitude toward the work and job performance. This implies that the attitude of employees toward their work affects their job performance. This finding suggests that improving job performance can be done by changing employees' attitudes toward their work. However, taking them singly, both elements of attitudes such as cognitive and affective attitude are correlated to the two elements such as task performance and contextual performance but not to the counterproductive behavior. Cognitive and affective attitudes are not correlated to counter-productive behavior.

V. Result and Discussion

The finding of this study pointed out that there is a correlation between the attitude of employees toward their work and their work performance. This finding brings us to the importance of attitude management. Managing the attitude means how the management improves their cognitive and emotional attitude toward the work. In this regard, the management must minimize the negative attitude and increase positive attitude, both cognitive and affective attitude. Increasing positive attitude will mean that management finds ways to improve their knowledge and skills toward the work and at the same time improves the work environment for them to love their work. Quarrey (2019) contended that a positive attitude energizes people to accomplish their work and consequently increase productivity. A positive attitude is not just about the feeling one has about the job but it is also about what one knows about the job. Knowledge of a job is an important factor that contributes to performance and it can affect the emotion of the person doing the job. The two-dimension, cognitive and affective

attitude can affect each other. When an employee does not have any idea about his job and how to go about his job may affect his feeling toward the job (Beswick, 2011). Once the feeling is affected, then it will affect his/her performance (Pervez, 2010). Managing work performance requires attitude management.

Work performance has been the primary concern of any organization because employees' performance can affect the status or the success of the organization. Thus, solving employees' performance problems may not be easy as we discuss it because it requires a broader outlook on the different aspects that may affect the employees' performance. Often time, management focuses their attention on the tangible aspect such as monetary benefits and other incentives to motivate employees to improve their performance but neglect to address the intangible elements of employees' contributing factor to performance which is their attitude. Studies have been conducted along with this concern. Khan and Ghauri (2014), Susanty, Maradipta, and Jie (2013) found the relationship between attitude and performance. The same finding was also forwarded by the study of Hettiarachchi and Jayarathna (2014) on the effect of attitude toward work performance.

Conclusion

After the data has been presented and analyzed, this study concludes that employees' attitude toward their work is considered high and there is also considered high. The study further found that their attitude toward work affects their work performance. The Pearson r correlation found that there is a correlation between attitude toward work and work performance, and therefore the hypothesis of the study is accepted. Thus, such a result concludes that enhancing the work performance of employees can be done through enhancing their attitude toward the work.

This study contributes to the discussion on organizational behavior theory. Topics related to organizational behavior must be broadened to include the topic of the effect of attitude toward human behavior. Motivation and work performance are just products of a positive attitude toward the work. The study also recognizes its limitation because of a limited number of the population included in the study. The next study needs to include a wider population.

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